

Determining the Ion Mobility and Ion Density of Perovskite Solar Cells with Impedance Spectroscopy

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Abstract

Mobile ions in metal halide perovskites are found to degrade perovskite solar cells (PSCs). Therefore, characterizing their density and mobility is crucial for improving the long-term performance of PSCs. A common method to characterize PSCs is impedance spectroscopy.

In the literature, the low-frequency (LF) feature of the PSC impedance response is related to ion dynamics and the high-frequency feature to electronic processes. Yet, why these features can vary over orders magnitude in terms of frequency and impedance is unclear.

In this work (see figure below), we identify the specific ion dynamics that drive the LF feature.^[1] We derive two separate analytical expressions that directly relate the frequency and magnitude of the LF feature to the ion density and ion mobility, respectively. The validity of both analytical expressions are confirmed through extensive drift-diffusion simulations, varying over 35 parameters.

Alternative formulas from the literature are also tested, but are found to be suboptimal. After the validation, we experimentally determine the ion density and mobility of a methylammonium lead iodide PSC. They are $3.0 \times 10^{21} \text{ m}^{-3}$ and $4 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively.

This new method, which depends on the low-frequency feature of the impedance spectrum, facilitates the precise and straightforward determination of the ion density and ion mobility in PSCs.

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References

[1] Elhorst, F. D.; Sebastián Alonso, J. E.; Bolink, H. J.; Koster, L. J. A. Determining the Ion Mobility in Perovskite Solar Cells from Impedance Spectroscopy, *ACS Energy Letters*, **10** (2025), 4574-4579.

Figure: Poster at NGSE10.